

eCoSimHPC: Large-scale Energy System Co-Simulation with High Performance Computing

bwRSE4HPC Project Proposal

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Scientific field:	Engineering
Subfield:	Energy Systems
Start:	01.10.2025
Duration:	4 months
Type of Work	HPC Porting
License:	-
Link:	-
Programming Language:	Python
Technologies:	Websockets, FMI, MPI/Dask
Target Cluster:	bwUniCluster, Horeka

1 Project Summary

The eCoSim (Energy System Co-Simulation) software – developed by the research group Energy System Analysis (ESA) at KIT-IAI – is designed to simulate and analyze coupled multi-modal energy systems [1]. Such energy systems include the electrical and heating grids of buildings, neighborhoods, and cities. The current framework makes use of network communications to distribute simulation modules across multiple machines [2], allowing users to run simulations across computers around the world [3]. The simulation modules make use of Functional Mock-up Units (FMU); precompiled simulation model binaries that keep models private as necessary. The main simulator makes use of the FMUs to coordinate and synchronize the simulation subsystems within the larger model.

2 Problem Statement

The computational demand for running larger (co-) simulation setups, e.g., of entire cities, requires the use of HPC clusters. Currently, the largest simulations are distributed across multiple machines. To perform a large city-scale simulation, more than 50,000 FMUs are needed. This requires access to a high-speed connection to data storage facilities to access FMUs.

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The eCoSim simulation framework is currently not designed for HPC environments and likely requires adjustments of its communication framework to work. Having access to HPC capabilities through a user-friendly interface is one of the main goals in the near future.

3 Suggested Solution

The existing eCoSim framework makes use of websocket-based communication between different computing systems to distribute the co-simulations. The bwHPC systems make use of Infiniband / Omni-path networking to communicate between nodes with additional TCP/IP support on top. eCoSim will need to be tested initially on bwHPC systems to ensure the current communication framework can be used. If so, initial performance measurements should be taken to establish a baseline and identify any bottlenecks that may occur during development.

Afterwards, the communication framework needs to be adapted to a more suitable infrastructure designed to operate on HPC systems. This includes, but is not limited to, MPI via the mpi4py framework or Dask, a library designed for parallel and distributed computing with additional tools for measuring performance. Then a direct comparison of performance can be made with the previous framework. Afterwards, the new framework can be tested on larger systems that require multiple nodes.

4 Milestones

The time frames set by the following milestones are relative and are likely to change with ongoing development.

Month 1: In the first month, the RSEs will attempt to run eCoSim out of the box on bwUni-Cluster to test the current communication infrastructure and establish the baseline performance of the system. During this phase, the RSEs will also identify any potential bottlenecks in the system that will be resolved during the development stage.

Month 2: In the second month, the RSEs will begin the redevelopment of the communication framework, making use of an appropriate communication infrastructure for HPC systems.

Month 3: During the third month, the RSEs will continue to develop the new communication framework and begin performance tests of the new infrastructure.

Month 4: The RSEs aim to finish development by the beginning of the fourth month, with mainly scaling being tested at this point. The eCoSim team and the RSEs will discuss the current state of the project and a possible scope for extension (milestone subject to change as needed).

5 Expected Contributions

The bwrSE4HPC team will tackle the milestones and objectives presented in Sec. 4. To ensure smooth operation, the eCoSim team should contribute assistance. In particular, we define the following tasks, for which the eCoSim team is responsible:

- Grant access to the code repository.
- Provide small simulations to test development with.
- Attend scheduled progress updates.
- Include deliverables provided in Sec. 4 when publishing the software, along with a persistent object identifier (e.g., through Zenodo). This can occur after the completion of the project.
- Joint publication of a journal paper with code release (see previous topic) with the bwrSE4HPC team.

6 Confidentiality Agreement & Copyright

The eCoSim software is closed source. It will be made available to the bwrSE4HPC team as part of this collaboration. The rights to the code for eCoSim and the derived eCoSimHPC belong to the ESA-IAI working group.

References

- [1] H. K. Çakmak, A. Kocher, H. Cheng, J. Kovačević, and V. Hagenmeyer, “Collaborative modelling and co-simulation for sector-coupled multi-energy system analysis with easimov-ecosim”, in [Kit bibliothek](#) (2025).
- [2] A. Erdmann, H. K. Çakmak, U. Kühnapfel, and V. Hagenmeyer, “A new communication concept for efficient configuration of energy systems integration co-simulation”, in [2019 IEEE/ACM 23rd International Symposium on Distributed Simulation and Real Time Applications \(DS-RT\)](#) (2019), pp. 1–8.
- [3] A. Kocher, J. Kovačević, A.-C. Süß, C. B. Saner, B. Dindar, M. A. Ehsan, H. K. Çakmak, and V. Hagenmeyer, “Privacy protection in collaborative geographically distributed co-simulation of multimodal energy systems”, in [Proceedings of the 15th ACM International Conference on Future and Sustainable Energy Systems](#), e-Energy '24 (2024), pp. 639–647.